

Study of Ground Water Table Fluctuations for Kachchh District of Gujarat

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ABSTRACT

Kachchh District of Gujarat has been divided into 9 talukas. However, the geology varies from taluka to taluka. Some of the talukas have sandy soil while some have sandy clay and some have clayey soil. Due to this the development of ground water varies from taluka to taluka.

Most of the surface water which is stored due to construction of various hydraulic structures like medium irrigation schemes, minor irrigations schemes, check dams and number of other micro-structures is percolated into the soil and becomes a part of the ground water.

Ground water consists of 90 percent of the water supply for domestic use as well as for irrigation purposes. Due to this it is very important that maximum quantity of surface water is stored and converted to ground water.

Through this paper it is attempted to study the pre-monsoon and post-monsoon water table fluctuations due to the storage of water in the dams and suggest methods to enhance the ground water recharge in the Kachchh District of Gujarat.

INTRODUCTION

Kachchh is an ancient land possessed of great antiquity which takes its name from its geographical characteristics and topographical features resembling a tortoise. It is located on the north west part of Gujarat.

The district stretches roughly from 22°44'11" (approx.) to 24°41'25" (approx.) north latitudes and 68°09'46" (approx.) and 71°54'47" (approx.) east longitudes. It is bounded on the north and north-west by Sindh (Pakistan), on the north-east by Rajasthan, on the east by the districts of Banaskantha and Mehsana, on the south-east

by Surendranagar district, on the south by the Gulf of Kutch and the Rajkot district and on the south-west and west by the Arabian Sea.

GEOLOGY OF KACHCHH

The soils of Kutch can be mainly classified into:

(1) Desert (2) alluvial sandy (3) medium black (4) saline alkaline

Though other types such as loamy, silty and clayey are also found at certain places, the northern part of the district is dominated by desert and sandy soils which are mostly salt affected soils. Proceeding southwards, the interior area is composed of either sandy or medium black soils. The southern part of the district comprising the coastal area around Mandavi and Mundra has saline soils suitable for cultivation. The eastern part is mostly plain with some rocky patches where the soil is sandy with clay and alluvial loam in some parts. The central portion is hilly and rocky with strips of cultivable lands along the lower slopes.

Table 1 Types of Soils

Sr.No.	Type of Soil	Taluka
1	Clayey	Mundra
2	Sandy Clay	Bhuj Anjar Rapar Nakhtrana
3	Clayey & Medium black	Lakhpat Mandvi Abdasa
4	Sandy, Clayey & Medium Black	Bhachau

Tube Wells

The following table shows the number of government tubewells in various talukas of Kachchh District.

Table 2 Number of Tube wells

Sr.no	Taluka	No.of tube wells
1	Anjar	13
2	Mandavi	21
3	Nakhtrana	34
4	Bhuj	57
5	Mundra	7
6	Bhachau	10
7	Rapar	10
8	Lakhpat	2
9	Total	154

Out of 154 tube wells drilled,129 have proved successful,39 of them have been installed with pumps and engines. Together all the tube wells irrigate about 10,441 hectares of land.

SURFACE WATER STORAGE

The rain water is stored in the form of surface storage in 20 medium irrigation schemes, 165 minor irrigation schemes as well as number of checkdams and other microstructures. The progress in the construction of these surface water storage structures is as follows:

Table 3 Irrigation Program

Period	Catchment area in sq.km.	Cost incurred in Rs.	Cross capacity added in Mcm.	Irrigation potential in hectares
Before 1951	1138	5,324,310	93	17,968
During first five year plan	876	9,620,965	74	14,616
During second five year plan	504	11,998,561	46	12,906
During Third five year plan	274	8,677,736	23	3,704
Total	2,792	35,621,572	236	49,194

GROUND WATER FLUCTUATIONS IN VARIOUS PARTS OF KACHCHH

SUMMARY

The number of medium irrigation schemes as well as minor irrigation schemes and check dams and other microstructures are responsible for the surface water storage. As the number of such structures has increased with the passage of years, the surface storage in the region has increased.

As most of the area consists of sandy soil and therefore most of the surface water stored is converted to ground water.

CONCLUSIONS

In the areas where the quantity of rainfall is better and there are more number of surface water storage structures, the quantity of ground water recharge is better and therefore, there is a slight rise in the level of ground water table in these regions.

In areas where the quantity of rainfall is very less and there are few number of surface water storage structures, the quantity of ground water recharge is poor and therefore, there is a pattern of ground water table declination in these regions.

Thus, an attempt should be made to increase the number of surface water storage structures and reduce the quantity of water being disposed off into the sea.

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ANNEXURES

1. Plate 1 Rivers and locations of medium irrigation schemes.
2. Plate 4 Geology of Kachchh District

Plate 1 Rivers and locations of medium irrigation schemes

Plate 2 Geology of Kachchh District

